

EXCHANGE RATE, INFLATION AND THE NIGERIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

The study analyzed the effect of exchange rate on Nigeria economic growth over the period of 1988- 2018. The main type of data used in this study is secondary; sourced from various publications of Central Bank of Nigeria. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) statistical technique was employed in this study to determine the impact of the exchange rate and inflation rate on economic growth. The findings revealed that economic growth is directly related to exchange rate and negatively related to inflation rate and it is also statistically significant at 5% level. Although, there is a positive relationship between exchange rate and a negative relationship between inflation and economic growth. The negative relationship between inflation and economic growth was statistically insignificant. The study recommends that the Central Bank of Nigeria should put in place a strict foreign exchange policy control to ensure that the value of Naira against other currency is properly determined.

Keywords: Exchange rate, Inflation rate, Trade Openness, Economic Growth Ordinary Least Square.

Introduction

Exchange Rate (EXR) is the price of a nation's currency in terms of another country currency. It is also regarded as the value of one country's currency in terms of another country currency. Thus, it has two components, namely; the domestic currency and a foreign currency, and can be quoted either directly or indirectly. In an indirect quotation, the price of a unit of domestic currency is expressed in terms of the foreign currency whereas in a direct quotation, the converse holds. Exchange Rates (EXRs) are determined in the foreign exchange market which is open to a wide range of different type of buyers and sellers where currency trading is continuous. A market-based Exchange Rate changes if the values of either of the two component currencies change. A currency will tend to become more valuable when the demand for it is greater than the available supply and become less valuable each time the demand is less than available supply.

Goldberg and Charles (2015) observed that Exchange Rate can influence both the total amount of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) that takes place and the allocation of investment spending across a range of countries. When a currency depreciates, it means that its value declines relative to the value of another country's currency. This Exchange Rate movement has two potential implications to Foreign Direct

Investment. First, it reduces that country's wages and production costs relative to those of its foreign counterparts. Other things being equal, the country experiencing real currency depreciation has enhanced “locational advantage” or attractiveness as a location for receiving productive capacity for investment. By this “relative wage” channel, the Exchange Rate depreciation improves the overall rate of return to foreigners contemplating overseas investment project in this country.

Exchange rate is a key variable in external sector because it linked external variables to domestic variables. Fluctuations in exchange rate is a reflection of changes in both foreign and domestic fundamentals such as foreign reserves, terms of trade, oil price, domestic price, government expenditure and interest rate differential. Studies have also shown that past values of exchange rate could explain its variations. the argument is anchored on the fact that exchange rate follows random walk because describe the trends into which non stationary economic variable fit in and can take any value and are affected by time and its past values could better mirror the present and future values of its exchange rather than other economic fundamentals like growth.

The effect of inflation rate in economic development is evidence in the works of (Ajakaiye & Odusola, 2001). To them understanding the sources of fluctuations in output and inflation is an important challenge to empirical macroeconomists. It is an issue taken up in a large number of recent studies in the developed nations, Latin America, and Asian countries. At the core of these issues is whether or not stabilization without recession is possible. While some theoretical models suggest that stabilization could be expansionary particularly for high inflation countries, others argue that stabilization without recession is rather difficult to achieve. The three major explanations of inflation include fiscal, monetary, and balance of payments aspects. While in the monetary aspect inflation is considered to be due to an increase in money supply, in the fiscal aspect, budget deficits are the fundamental cause of inflation in countries with prolonged high inflation. However, the fiscal aspect is closely linked to monetary explanations of inflation since government deficits are often financed by money creation in developing countries.

Several attempts have been made to conduct systematic econometric studies on the movements in output and inflation and their dynamics in Nigeria. However, many of these earlier studies were based on either simulation analysis or regression.

On real exchange rate and GDP, (Edwards, 1989) contended in his study when he regressed the GDP on measure of the nominal and real exchange rates, government spending, the terms of trade and measures of money growth. He observed that devaluation tended to reduce the output in the short term even where other factors

remained constant. This is in line with the view of the researcher that exchange rate policies strengthen economic development.

Statement of the Problem

The problem associated with utilization of exchange rate policies and economic growth is dwarf incessant increases inflation rate and harsh business environment with attendance upsurge in Nigeria's political terrain thereby affecting exchange rate policies. It also implies that the performance of the economy is still fluctuating having been affected by variables like the level of exchange rate and investments needed to improve in order to achieve economic goals.

Analysis of Nigeria's exchange rate since the early 1960s shows that there has been a continuous increase from one pound to a US dollar in 1960 to a current rate of 360 naira to a US dollar. Due to the poor economic performance and surging debt burden, the exchange rate skyrocketed significantly during the early 1990's. However, at US\$5.353 in 1988, it rose marginally to US\$7.65 billion in 1989. By 2017 it was 305.5 naira to a US\$ dollar. To date, there has not been sufficient research that examines the connection between actual exchange rate and inflation rate on economic growth.

A cursory look into the literature indicates that studies that have examined causality among exchange rate (EXR) and inflation rate (INF) and growth remains mixed as their method of analysis varied. Also, in the context of the dwindling revenue obtained from the main foreign exchange earner (crude oil) of Nigeria, it becomes appropriate to re-examine the form of relationship between exchange rate and economic growth. It is based on this backdrop that this study in particular, will focus on finding the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth from 1988 to 2017.

Research Question

The following research questions will be advanced to serve as a guide to this research work

1. What is the effect of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria?
2. Does inflation rate has any significant influence on the Nigerian economic growth?
3. What is the relationship between trade openness and Nigeria's economic growth?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses expressed in null form will be advanced to give direction to this research work

- H_0 : Exchange rate has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
 H_0 : Inflation rate does not significantly influence economic growth in Nigeria
 H_0 : There is no significant relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Nigeria.

Literature Review

The Effect of Inflation and Real Exchange Rate Policy on Economic Development

The effect of inflation rate in economic development is evidenced in the works of (Ajakaiye & Odusola, 2001). To them understanding the sources of fluctuations in output and inflation is an important challenge to empirical macroeconomists. It is an issue taken up in a large number of recent studies in the developed nations, Latin America, and Asian countries. At the core of these issues is whether or not stabilization without recession is possible. While some theoretical models suggest that stabilization could be expansionary particularly for high inflation countries, others argue that stabilization without recession is rather difficult to achieve. The three major explanations of inflation include fiscal, monetary, and balance of payments aspects. While in the monetary aspect inflation is considered to be due to an increase in money supply, in the fiscal aspect, budget deficits are the fundamental cause of inflation in countries with prolonged high inflation. However, the fiscal aspect is closely linked to monetary explanations of inflation since government deficits are often financed by money creation in developing countries.

Again Again Ajakaiye & Odusola, 2001, in their study of the balance of payments aspect, emphasizes a placed on the exchange rate.. Simply, the exchange rate collapses bring about inflation either through higher import prices and increase in inflationary expectations which are often accommodated through an accelerated wage indexation mechanism.

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In a related study, Agenor, 1991 using a sample of twenty three (23) developing countries, regressed output growth contemporaneous and lagged levels of the real exchange rate and on deviations of actual changes from expected ones in the real exchange rate, government spending, the money supply, and foreign income. The results showed that surprises in real exchange rate depreciation actually boosted output growth, but that depreciations of the level of the real exchange rate exerted a contractionary effect.

Theoretical Framework

The neoclassical growth theory and the traditional flow model of exchange rate are used as the framework of analysis in this study.

The Neoclassical Growth Theory

The growth model of the neoclassicists otherwise known as the Solow-Swan or

Exogenous Growth is a form of long-run economic model designed in the neo-classical economics framework. In analyzing economic growth in relation to long run, the model considered technological progress, population expansion, capital accumulation and productivity in the process of development. The neo-classical proposition was an expansion to the work of Harrod-Domar in 1946 which incorporated productivity into the growth equation. Within the context of Solow-model, recent capital is more important than previous capital in the light of the fact that capital is generated base on recognized innovation. Innovation enhances with time and fresh capital will be more efficient than vintage capital. Growth rate is decided outside the model in the neo-classical growth hypothesis. A typical expectation of this model is that an economy will dependably come together towards stable state that relies just on the pace of technical advancement in addition to the rate of workforce expansion.

The general implication of exchange rate on the Solow growth thesis can be viewed by analyzing the individual effects of exchange rate, trade openness theories on the Solow growth hypothesis. According to the theory, trade will be beneficial to a trading country if they engage in the production and exportation of goods in which they have comparative advantage and adopt a proper well guided exchange rate regime.

The traditional flow model of exchange rate postulates that the exchange rate is determined by the forces of supply and demand for foreign exchange. The traditional flow model postulates that increase in domestic prices relative to foreign prices leads to exchange rate depreciation because increase in domestic prices feed into costs thereby making exports costly and highly uncompetitive. The model prescribes that a country that intends to strengthen its exchange rate must raise interest rate, lower prices, and reduce real growth..

Methodology of the Study

This study adopted an ex-post facto research design in examining the effect of exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria from 1988 to 2017. The data applied in this study were secondary in nature and were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin of 2017. The dependent variable is Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). The independent variable is Real Exchange Rate (REXR). Inflation (INF) and trade openness (TOP) were introduced in the models as control variables capable of influencing economic growth. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was adopted to analyze the data collected.

Model Specification

The model specify for this study is as follows:

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Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin of 2015. The data were on annual basis as contained in the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin. The dependent variables are Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) and Manufacturing Capacity Utilization (MCU). The independent variable is Real Exchange Rate (REXR) and proxy for exchange rate policy. Inflation (INF) and Interest Rate (BLR) were introduced in the models as control variables capable of influencing economic growth indicators.

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$$RGDP_t + \beta_0 + \beta_1 REXR_t + \beta_2 INF_t + \beta_3 TOP_t + U$$

Where:

$RGDP_t$ = Real Gross domestic product in time t

$REXR_t$ = Real Exchange rate in time t

INF_t = Inflation in time t

TOP_t = Trade openness proxy by export and import in time t

U = error term

$\beta_0 - \beta_1$ are the parameter of the exogenous variables

Apriori expectation

$\beta_0 < \text{or} > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$, and $\beta_2 < 0$

Data Analysis and Presentation

Unit Root Test:

Table 1: Augmented Dickey-Fuller results (1988-2017)

Variables	t-statistics	5% critical value	1% critical value	Remark
RGDP	-4.078535	-3.603202	-4.374307	I(2)
REXR	-3.064795	-2.971853	-3.689194	I(1)
INF	-4.660128	-2.971853	-3.689194	I(1)
TOP	-3.886025	-3.622033	-4.416345	I(1)

Source: Author's computation(E-views9)

The result from table 1 using augmented Dickey Fuller test shows that, REXR, INF, and TOP are stationary at first difference while RGDP is stationary at second difference. At first differencing, the calculated ADF test statistics for REXR, INF & TOP are greater than their critical values at 5% level of significant, so we reject the null hypothesis of unit root and conclude that these variables are stationary at first difference I(1).

Co-Integration Test: Cointegration among time series variables suggests that series may behave in different way in the short run but that they will converge towards common equilibrium behavior in the long run. According to Engle and Granger (1987), set of time series are cointegrated when their residual is stationary. The stationarity of residual implies the existence of a long run stable relationship between RGDP and REXR

Table 2: Cointegration Test

	t-statistics	5% critical value	remark
ADF	-1.961004	-2.967767	Not Stationary

Source: Author's computation (Eviews9)

From the results obtained, the ADF test statistic value of -1.961004 for the residuals is lower than the 5% critical ADF value of -2.967767, indicating non-stationarity of the residual value. So, we conclude that there exists no long run relationship among our variables that is to say that our variables are not cointegrated.

Table 3: OLS regression

Dependent Variable: RGDP
Method: Least Squares
Date: 08/23/20 Time: 04:34
Sample: 1988 2017
Included observations: 30

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
REXR	152.5375	24.27557	6.283579	0.0000
INF	-86.07983	82.25864	-1.046453	0.3050
TOP	194.9478	48.65839	4.006457	0.0005
C	19486.69	3567.315	5.462566	0.0000
R-squared	0.872374	Mean dependent var		36947.35
Adjusted R-squared	0.857648	S.D. dependent var		18614.54
S.E. of regression	7023.180	Akaike info criterion		20.67539
Sum squared resid	1.28E+09	Schwarz criterion		20.86221
Log likelihood	-306.1308	Hannan-Quinn criter.		20.73515
F-statistic	59.24022	Durbin-Watson stat		0.498506
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Discussion of Findings

From table 3, the result of the OLS shows that exchange rate (REXR) and trade openness (TOP) have a significant positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria. A percentage increase in REXR and TOP will increase RGDP by 152.54% and 194.95% respectively. the coefficient of inflation is -86.0798 and this reveals a negative relationship between inflation and Nigeria's economic growth. Although this negative relationship is insignificant because our probability value of 0.3050 is greater than 0.05. These findings are similar to the findings of Anyanwu, F., Ananwude, A., & Okoye, N. (2017), who in their work discovered a positive relationship between exchange rate and economic growth and a negative relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria. However, the findings are not in line with the the result of Imoisi, Uzomba and Olatunji (2010) and Adelowokan, Adesoye and Balogun (2015) who in their various works discovered a negative relationship between real exchange rate and economic growth. The Adjusted R-squared reveals that 85.8% changes in RGDP was attributed to the joint variations in real exchange rate, inflation rate and trade openness. This is statistically significant (5% significance level) judging by the F-statistic of 59.24 which exhibits that the changes in RGDP was significantly explained by the independent variables within the period studied. The Durbin Watson statistic of 0.499 is not quite bad.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One

Restatement of Research Hypothesis

H_0 : Exchange rate has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

From Table 3, REXR p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. In the light of this, the null hypothesis that real exchange rate has no significant effect on Nigeria's economic growth is rejected while the alternate hypothesis accepted.

Hypothesis Two

Restatement of Research Hypothesis

H_0 : Inflation rate does not significantly influence economic growth in Nigeria

From Table 3, INF p-value of 0.3050 is greater than 0.05. In the light of this, the null hypothesis that Inflation rate does not significantly influence economic growth in Nigeria is accepted.

Hypothesis Three

Restatement of Research Hypothesis

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Nigeria.

From Table 3, TOP p-value of 0.0005 is less than 0.05. In the light of this, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Nigeria is rejected while the alternate hypothesis accepted. So, we conclude that there is a significant relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of exchange rate on Nigeria economic growth. The study sought to find out the relationship between exchange rate, inflation and economic growth. Real gross domestic product was used as a proxy for economic growth which is the dependent variable while exchange rate, trade openness and inflation rate were the independent variables.

The Engle and Granger co-integration test was used to test the existence of a long run relationship between exchange rate and economic growth. The null hypothesis of no-cointegration was accepted as the results showed that there is no long run relationship between exchange rate and economic growth. The OLS regression was used to provide answers to the research questions. The study hypothesis was tested using probability-values of the OLS regressions. From our findings, the study makes the following recommendation.

- The Central Bank of Nigeria should put in place a strict foreign exchange policy control to ensure that the value of Naira against other currency is properly determined. Unethical practices by banks leading to depreciation of the Naira should be investigated and erring operators sanctioned accordingly.
- Coherency of trade policy (tariffs and non tariff barriers) with trade promotion policies should be properly formulated. In other to achieve this, vigorous export promotion policy of finished and unfinished products should be pursued.

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